

Christ Way Ministries International

also known as “Also known as Abundant Life People”

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Entry tags: yoruba, Pentecostal, Religious Group, Language, English

Christ Way Ministries International is a Pentecostal Church founded in November, 1992 having up to 84 churches scattered all over Southwestern Nigeria. Christ Way Ministries International started as Hospital Christian Fellowship in the late 70s by few Hospital Workers who loved the Lord, desired to grow spiritually and had burden to win others for Christ. It commenced as a church with 90 members at its present National Headquarters, located at Iredapo Quarters in Ile-Ife. The Ministry focuses on evangelism, spiritual growth, family life and personal development of members, which have contributed immensely to her present growth of about 7000 in membership with 84 branches (local churches and Fellowship centres in higher institutions) in 7 states of Nigeria. The immediate past General Overseer is Pastor (Dr.) Samuel Odunlami Orioke, who voluntarily retired from active medical practice to devote himself more to the ministry. The Headquarters' office is in Ile Ife, Nigeria with over 150 pastors in its workforce. Christ Way Ministries International is a Pentecostal Church founded in November, 1992 with up to 84 churches scattered all over Southwestern Nigeria. Christ Way Ministries International started as a Hospital Christian Fellowship in the late 70s by a few Hospital Workers who loved the Lord, desired to grow spiritually, and had the burden to win others for Christ. It commenced as a church with 90 members at its present National Headquarters, located at Iredapo Quarters in Ile-Ife. The Ministry focuses on evangelism, spiritual growth, family life, and personal development of members, which have contributed immensely to her present growth of about 7000 in membership with 84 branches (local churches and Fellowship centers in higher institutions) in 7 states of Nigeria. The immediate past General Overseer is Pastor (Dr.) Samuel Odunlami Orioke, who voluntarily retired from active medical practice to devote himself more to the ministry. The Headquarters office is in Ile Ife, Nigeria with over 150 pastors in its workforce. Christ Way Ministries International (CWMI) is more prevalent in the Southwestern part of Nigeria but there are scattered branches in the Midwestern Nigeria and a new branch in Australia. There are diaspora members in the United States of America, the United Kingdom, the United Arab Emirates, and Canada. A brief background history of the Hospital Christian Fellowship that led to the formation of Christ Way Church is in order. Hospital Christian Fellowship began as a result of the activities of some young Christian graduates from Universities in Nigeria in the middle of the 1970s, who found jobs in the teaching hospital, and began a fellowship group in Ilé-Ifè. This fellowship group, which started specifically in 1976, comprised of young people from various denominations (Anglican, Baptist, and Methodist,) who were mainly hospital workers in Ilé-Ifè. Their goal was to meet and discuss the Bible and evangelize their immediate hospital environment. The names of these young graduates at that time are: Bádé Nwakpa (a Pharmacist), Niyi Arówólò (an Engineer), Philip O. Ògúnnówò (a Medical Doctor), Christopher Òpápéjú (a Secondary School teacher) and his wife OpéOlúwa Òpápéjú (a hospital secretarial staff) and finally Uche Onwudiegu (a Medical Doctor). At its initial stage, the group adopted a rotational presidency. Niyi Arówólò was the first president; at the expiry of his tenure, Philip O. Ògúnnówò took over from him and was the president until when Samuel Odúnlámi Oríòkè joined the group in 1983. In October, 1983, Odúnlámi Oríòkè took over as the president after a three-day fast and he maintained the position until 1992 when the fellowship changed its status to a Church. The hospital group met for their fellowship activities on the premises of the Seventh Day Adventist (henceforth SDA) Hospital, which the Federal Government acquired from the SDA mission and made an extension of the Ife University Teaching Hospital Complex (IUTHC), to train medical students. The group met on Tuesdays and Thursdays. Tuesdays were for Bible study, while Thursdays were for prayer meetings. The fellowship was meeting inside one of the School of Nursing's classrooms. When

the classroom was in use by the School of Nursing, the fellowship group often moved to other available venues, such as the General Outpatient Department (GOPD) or the corridor of the Hospital Laboratory Department. During the early days of the meetings, the hospital management did not oppose the activities of the members of the group nor did they interfere with their meetings, until the group grew. Until Odúnlámi Oriòkè joined in 1983, the Hospital Christian Fellowship (HCF) had just a few members, no more than 15 in all. By the time he joined the group, he introduced radical evangelism within and outside the hospital premises. What is meant by radical evangelism here is the use of different methods such as tract distribution (especially Four Spiritual Laws), bus evangelism, and drama evangelism and so on, to present the gospel to the people. Evangelism was no longer confined to the four walls of the hospital; coupled with bed-to-bed hospital evangelism, there was the house-to-house evangelism, which took the group out of the hospital premises into the community around the hospital. Some members of the SDA church became members of the fellowship. This was the beginning of the travail of the fellowship, because the SDA Church's council rose up and in fact instigated the hospital management to take a stand against the fellowship. The leaders of the fellowship at the time who were also medical doctors in the same hospital pleaded with the hospital management. The matter dragged on until the end of 1986 when the fellowship was eventually kicked out of the hospital premises. Some of the members who were head teachers at the SDA Grammar School (High School) gave the leadership of the fellowship permission to use the school's classrooms for its weekly activities. In 1988, when the Federal Government of Nigeria returned back the hospital and the school initially taken from them, the SDA church council served the Fellowship with a note to vacate the premises. This meant that the group was going to lose its identity by striking out the phrase, "Hospital Christian," from its name. When the fellowship moved from the hospital premises to the school premises, many non-hospital workers, such as Akin Ìgè, T.O. Oyèbísí, Tùndé Okùnádé, and other influential individuals, had joined the group and also occupied leadership positions of the fellowship. Some members of the fellowship who belonged to the Methodist Church of Nigeria, Obalùfòn, Ilé-Ìfè, appealed to their church's council to grant permission for the fellowship to hold its weekly meetings on Methodist property. The Church Council granted temporary permission in 1988. The fellowship changed its name to Christ Way Fellowship (CWF) at the end of the year 1988. Because the permission granted the fellowship was not stipulated in writing, some members of the Methodist Church who felt threatened by the activities of the fellowship complained about the inconvenience created by the CWF. The CWF moved out of the Methodist Church at the end of 1989 and established its home where its present headquarters is located at Temipemi Street, Iredapo Quarters, Ilé-Ìfè. The place is a three-acre land with an old church and an uncompleted apartment complex within it. The place was bought from its original owner, who was also using it for the church's activities. The fellowship leaders, having purchased this property where fellowship activities could be held without any hindrance, began to operate as a pseudo-church. I use the word pseudo here because the organization had already been operating as a church without any official recognition by the Federal Government of Nigeria. Fellowship activities were no longer restricted to two days of the week, but were extended to about four days, namely Mondays, Prayer Meetings; Tuesdays, Bible Study; Thursdays, Deliverance Hour, and Sundays, Home Cell leaders' meetings (House Fellowship). Home Cell was already a part of the programs of the HCF when they met at the hospital premises. Seeing all these kinds of activities, many church leaders in the town of Ilé-Ìfè had begun to insinuate that Odún Oriòkè, the leader of the CWF, was already nursing the ambition to start a church. Maybe they were correct, as events that led to the formation of the church confirmed what the public and some members of the Orthodox churches had already suspected.

Date Range: 1992 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Southwestern and West Central regions of Nigeria

Region tags: Southwest Nigeria, Nigeria, Oyo state, Ogun State, Ekiti State, Osun state, Osun State, Kwara state, Lagos, Ondo state, Oyo state

This map includes the approximate regions of

Southwest/Western Nigeria and is comprised of the following states: Lagos, Ogun, Oyo, Osun, Ondo, Ekiti, and Benin states. The additional inclusion of the West Central region state of Kwara is to the north of these states.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: David O. Ogungbile, *Odun Orioke: A Quintessential Leader, Statesman and Life-Coach*, Ibadan, Nigeria: Ranttie Royal Publishers, First Edition, 2023

Notes: This is a book written as a biographical memoir in honour of the pioneer General Overseer when he turned 70 years old on September 5, 2023. The author of the book chronicles the life history ranging from early background to the time Odun Orioke became the leader of Christ Way Fellowship which metamorphosed into Christ Way Ministries International, his roles in taking the church from scratch to where it has reached now, and his challenges and so on, are all contained in the book. The detailed history of the Church is also contained in the book.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: Gbadegesin, Enoch. "Comparative Analysis of Gift Exchange among a Pentecostal Christian Denomination and an Indigenous Religious Tradition in Ile-Ife, Nigeria." (2014) Diss., Rice University. <https://hdl.handle.net/1911/76731>.
- Source 1 Description: This dissertation is a comparative analysis of the gift and how it impacts on interpersonal relationship among the Yoruba of Nigeria. The dissertation examines gift exchange as it is practiced among the worshippers of Ògún deity usually commemorated as an annual Olójó festival in comparison with Christ Way Church International a member of Pentecostal Charismatic group in Ilé-Ife. In particular, the dissertation analyses a) the gift, its definition and the theoretical propositions by the anthropologists and sociologists and the principles that govern its practice; b) ethnographically, the Yoruba experience and expression of the gift, at the social, political, economic and ritual levels of interaction among immediate group and with other group of people; c) the patterns of interpersonal relationship that exists between the Òrìsà worshippers and Pentecostal Charismatic Christians using the two focused religious groups in Ilé-Ife as test case; d) how gift exchange practices can be means of creating and maintaining boundaries, and how that can lead to identity formation between different religious groups; in short how gift and reciprocity can be means of exclusion by bringing Annette Weiner's Inalienable Possessions in conversation with Marcel Mauss's The Gift; e) the different senses and contexts in which the religious groups can use gift exchange practices to bring about solidarity and harmony in the Yorùbá society.
- Source 1 URL: <https://christwayministries.org/>
- Source 1 Description: This is the official website of the organization.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.o-bible.com/kjv.html>
- Source 1 Description: English Bible reference online depending on the versions adopted

Notes: This Christian group believes in the Bible as the final authority for guiding and gauging believers' lives and conducts

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: I have argued elsewhere that the presence of Christ Way Church International serves as a threat to African Indigenous Religious practice in Ile-Ife, where the headquarters of the church is located. There is a kind of religious rhetoric between Christ Way Church International and traditional religious worshippers in Ile-Ife.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact does not necessarily lead to violence between the two religions but the two do not accommodate each other. In fact, Christ Way Church International constantly prays for the complete eradication of Orisa or Traditional Religious worship in Ile-Ife.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: The cultural contact is highly engaging especially with the way Christ Way Church International members always go out to evangelize the "religious other" with the ultimate aim of converting them to Jesus Christ.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: There is no violence. Christ Way Church Members have been strictly warned to not engage in physical or verbal altercations that may lead to violence against the traditional religious worshippers either in Ile-Ife or everywhere the churches are located.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: As said above, Christ Way Church Leadership preaches against religious violence.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: By voluntarily joining the group through personal or religious conviction

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Through preaching to non-members about their religious beliefs and practices

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: The religious leaders in the group are expected to tell others about Christ and invite them to the church if they are so inclined.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: All adherents of the group are enjoined to profess their faith and inform others about the gift of salvation in Jesus Christ. Those it is not a matter of compulsion they are admonished to take part in the task of evangelism.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: The religious professionals in the group are otherwise known as the church leaders. They are all expected to be involved in missionary work at least in their locality.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: The group does not coerce members to get involved in proselytization.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: Apostates are usually ostracized

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– No

Notes: Though the group ostracises apostates, they still pray for their repentance. As a result, they do not shun or vilify them.

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

Notes: Apostates in the group do not receive corporal punishments.

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that apostates will be punished by the supreme being on the final day of judgement if they do not repent before their death.

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– No

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– No

↳ Other divine punishment:

– Yes [specify]: The group believes that apostates will receive divine punishment on the final day of judgement.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 7500

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 3

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are recognised leaders in the religious group. The group has local (parish) pastors, Area pastors, Zonal pastors, Assistant General Overseers, Deputy General Overseers and the General Overseer who is the human head of the church. The General Overseer is responsible to the Christ who is the spiritual head of the church.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: There is a clear hierarchical order among the church leaders of the Christ Way Ministries.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: There is usually a pastor who leads each local assembly (congregation) of the group. The pastor may be assisted by one or more junior pastors, deacons and other leaders of service departments within the church. The leadership layers/strata in each assembly depends on the size of each local assembly.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: Although each church has its local leadership, churches in each area are grouped together so that an area/zonal pastor coordinates the activities of the churches within his/her jurisdiction.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

Notes: This is as highlighted above.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The general overseer oversees the activities of all the church branches

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Important decisions in the church are sometimes taken by the General overseer with support from his deputies and Assistant General overseers. However, the General Overseer could also lead the church in some directions as instructed by the Holy Spirit.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 8

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Notes: The group does not attribute supernatural powers to the leaders although the members admit the leaders could be used by the supreme being to perform supernatural feats as it is fitting to the supreme being from time to time. The group therefore believes that the sufficiency of the leaders is not in themselves but in the supreme being.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: The religious leaders in the group are chosen by the leaders who are superior to them in the church.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

Notes: Pastors are posted to their local assemblies by the top hierarchy of the church. However, there has been one transition between the founding General Overseer and the current one. The founding overseer was part of the crucial decision of determining his successor.

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

Notes: This is not the sole decision of the retinue of the leader. Succession is done by the cadre of leaders in consultation with the General Overseer of the group.

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

Notes: There is a level of involvement of all leaders in the process which leads to the emergence of the new leader.

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

Notes: Politicians are not involved in the affairs of the church.

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

Notes: The prayers offered by the entire membership of the church is a significant part of the leadership/recruitment selection process.

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: This is a vital part of the leadership selection process in the church

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

Notes: Though leaders are considered fallible in the religious group, members are not in the habit of accusing their leaders for wrongdoing. This is because the leaders are self aware and always conduct themselves in a respectable manner.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:
– No

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:
– No
Notes: This does not usually happen in the religious group

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:
– No
Notes: Political leaders do not interfere in the affairs of the group.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:
– Yes

↳ Are they oral:
– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:
– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:
– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Through the inspiration of the Holy Spirit, the third person of the Trinity

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: The group does not alter the bible. They believe that the bible is accurate in all matters. It is seen as authoritative as they submit to its pronouncement in all their endeavours.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: Although the church pastors and leaders interpret the bible to the group members, the members too are not forbidden from reading, studying and interpreting the bible as they gain understanding of its contents.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: There are church buildings in all the geographical places where the churches are located and there is a central Camping ground where structures for worship and accommodations are being constructed

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 50

Notes: In each church premises of then group, at least 50% of the entire landmass is taken up by the church building.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 30

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 15

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 15

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 10

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 40

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Sites dedicated to sacred practices in the group include the church altars and the church buildings

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: Pilgrimages are not compulsory in the group. Members in the church branches are however encouraged to attend joint camp programmes of the church at their central camp ground in Ile-Ife. This is strictly for religious purposes.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: As far as this religious group is concerned and perhaps based on the understanding of the reading of their scripture, the spirit-mind is stronger and has qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

Notes: The religious group believes that both spirit-mind and body are coeval and cannot be separated. In fact, it is the belief of the religious group that the spirit controls the body and often dictates what the body does from time to time according to their religious sensibility. They are fond of teaching about Spirit-controlled body or life; making body to stand for life. However, they believe that Spirit-mind cannot be seen with physical eyes. ; hence, it is immaterial in that sense.

Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: Spirit and body is not conceived in Cartesian term but both the spirit and body are assumed to be one and that spirit controls the body, while body houses the spirit.

– Yes

Notes: Spirit-mind is stronger and greater than other body parts. The religious group assumes that the

body cannot do any qualitatively different thing than what is assigned by the spirit. They often quote a verse in the Bible to support this belief, John 6: 63, It is the spirit that quickeneth; the flesh profiteth nothing: the words that I speak unto you, they are spirit, and they are life.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: In a sense, they believe that the Spirit-mind is non-material, and ontologically distinct from the body. They, however, believe that the body cannot be understood and appreciated without the spirit-mind.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The religious group believes that the body can both be possessed by good and evil spirits. The group believes that when the godly spirit is in operation in any being, such individuals conduct themselves in pleasant manners, exhibiting love and all good deeds. However, when the evil spirit takes control of humans, such humans exhibit all manner of negative and anti-social behaviours. It is the physical bodies of such beings so possessed by any of these spirits that carries out the bidding of the good/godly or evil spirits inhabiting them.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Dead bodies are usually embalmed if the dead is an adult or buried immediately if the dead is a baby or child. More often than not dead bodies are washed after embalment before they are eventually dressed, are kept in a coffin, and finally for burial.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Christ Way Ministries International has not gotten its cemetery but the leaders of the church usually make arrangements with other older Christian churches to use their cemetery. The Church is planning to own a cemetery.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: Individuals may decide to be buried at home

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: May be in front of the house or back or sides depending on the preference of an individual

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The Church members believe in the Supreme Being who is God, the creator of the whole universe, overseeing, directing, coordinating, and supervising the affairs of humans and non-humans in the world.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Compassionate, kind, loving, all-knowing, all-powerful, present everywhere and a great provider

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme high god creates the world and everything in it, hence, possesses the knowledge of the world and things outside the world

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Yes [specify]: Through the scripture and through prophets who are gifted in seeing to the future

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ, Holy Spirit, and the Angels are regarded as supernatural beings but while Jesus and the Holy Spirit are regarded as higher and greater than human beings, the angels are

regarded as servants that can serve the purpose of humans in the world. Devils and his demons are regarded as fallen angels

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Notes: All believers are regarded as equals before God. There is also a belief in the priesthood of all believers

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: There are Pastors over the members and the pastors are organized hierarchically such as the General Overseer, Deputy General Overseers (not more than two), Assistant General Overseers (could be up to three), Zonal Pastors, 14 at present (in charge of each Zone that the church is divided), Area pastors (in-charge of all areas the church is divided), Pastors in-charge (currently the church has about 160 pastors), deacons and deaconesses in all the churches (more than two hundred as at present), Unit leaders and the church members.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are believed to dwell in heavenly places but could interact and interfere with the human world at any time. Human beings dwell on earth and operate on earth. However, the devil and his agents are considered to dwell in the atmosphere and in the world of humans always causing havoc.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

– Yes

Notes: Jesus is considered to be fully human and divine.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: The Supreme high god is not anthropomorphic but could be described by using human features as also shown in the Bible, the primary scripture of the Church

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: The Supreme high god is regarded as occupying everywhere (omnipresent).

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: The Supreme high god is regarded as occupying heaven and earth and could be found anywhere at any time as aptly described in Psalms 139

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: The supreme high god is being described as king though following the cultural belief of the African people within which the church emerges.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: The king is seen as a cultural and traditional authority over his domain. However, it is a common believe among Christ Way Ministries members just like any Yoruba persons that monarchs are God' s representative to rule over the people in their domains.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: The supreme high god takes care of all people according to the belief of Christ Way Ministries International.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: Because of their staunch belief in the Bible as authoritative, the supreme high god is unquestionably good.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Christ Way Ministries International regards supreme high god as benevolent, powerful, kind, compassionate and loving.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Since he is the creator of all that is, Christ Way Ministries believe that the supreme high god has knowledge of everything and anything.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: The supreme god's knowledge is unlimited. He is the creator of all things. This is part of the doctrine of Christ Way Ministries International

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god is conceived as knowing all things

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region because he creates all things and knows all things

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: His eyes run to and fro the whole earth

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Because he is supreme, and omniscient, he can see anybody anywhere in the dark or at home.

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: He knows the intent and plan of anybody's heart including hidden motives

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: He knows one's basic character because he is believed to form human being in his own image.

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god knows what will happen to anyone and Christ Way Ministries International members often quote Jeremiah 29:11, which says: For I know the thoughts that I think toward you, saith the LORD, thoughts of peace, and not of evil, to give you an expected end, to strengthen this belief

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Since he is the creator, the church believes that he has other knowledge of this world not known to any mortal. For example, hidden things or elements or planets not yet known to anybody. Christ Way Ministries International members often cite Deuteronomy 29:29 that says, The secret things belong unto the LORD our God: but those things which are revealed belong unto us and to our children for ever, that we may do all the words of this law.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: He is believed to have the power to control the world the way he likes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the supreme high god rewards good behaviours with blessings and bad behaviours with curses.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the supreme high god can punish the evil humans do. This punishment can both be meted out in this life and in the after life.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: According to the Christian doctrine that Christ Way Ministries International subscribes, God is directly involved in the affairs of the world.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: God is known to the believers to show love, compassion, kind and benevolence.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that if people disobey the supreme high God, he could get angry and send punishment just like he did to Adam and Eve in the Garden of Eden and during the time of Noah and so on.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Notes: The group believes that the supreme high God does not possess hunger. This believe is hinged on the fact that there is no where in the Bible that shows that high God possesses hunger. In fact, Psalms 50:8-14, state that the high God does not possess hunger.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: The group believes that only the high god must be worshipped. They hold the believe that no other created being or other supernatural being is worthy of worship. Worshipping other supernatural beings apart from the supreme high God is tantamount to engaging in Idol worship, which is a great offence to the high god.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: High God can decide to communicate with the living the way he chooses; there is no restriction to how he communicates with the living

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: Human spirits began after creation of heaven and earth according to the Bible that Christ Way Ministries International subscribes to. Genesis 1:1ff

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

Notes: The group does not hold the believe that non-human supernatural beings are present in the world. They agree that the non-human supernatural spirits which exist are either ministering spirits in the supreme being's theocratic government or those who fell with Lucifer (the Devil) when he sought to exalt his throne above that of the supreme being. They accept the view that all things began to exist after creation.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: The group believes that Jesus Christ is the only individual who is both human and divine at the same time.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: The group believes in the trinity which comprises of God the father, the son and the Holy Spirit. However, they also hold the belief that Satan, demons and supernatural wicked beings exist that must be fought against constantly in prayer. Ephesians 6;11-18; I Peter 5: 7-8

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that God monitors the behaviours of every human being. They also believe that He is going to judge every human action and inaction at the end of life.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Christ Way Ministries teaches that the supernatural monitors human behavior and judges it appropriately

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Christ Way Ministries believes that certain foods are to be avoided so as not to contaminate oneself especially as found in the Old Testament. Though Paul tried to modify this in the New Testament some Christ Way Ministries members try to avoid certain fatty and other which constitute health risks to those who ingest them. They take their personal health serious as many of their members are health workers, including their founding pastor who is a medical doctor by training.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that sacred spaces such as the Temple, and altar are to be hallowed and not to be treated casually and irreverently.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: The temple of worship and altar are considered sacred and must not be desecrated.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The group believes that Jesus, Holy Spirit and Angels of God do care about God's creation especially Christians. This believe is consistent with the injunctions contained in the Bible

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: The group affirms the saying of Jesus Christ on the topic that He did not come to destroy but to save the world. Therefore, they strongly disapprove of the murder of coreligionists.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: See answer above

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the blood of members of the opposing side/other faiths should not be shed. Exodus 20:13

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes the injunction of both the Old and New Testaments that there should be no sexual intercourse with any woman or man who is not legally married to one

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Incest is detested and highly condemned by the authority of the church based on the Biblical injunction as found in Leviticus 18:1ff

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: All forms of sexual practices that do not conform with the Biblical practices such as Homosexuality, bestiality, fornications, and others are heavily condemned and frowned against and they are not taken lightly. Bible passages such as Leviticus 18:, 20:23; Romans 1: 26-27 and so on are often quoted by the church to show that God is against these sexual acts.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: The group upholds the biblical injunction which states that "all liars shall have their part in the lake of hell."

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: The group upholds the biblical injunction which says when you take an oath, you must fulfil it because God does not like anyone who swear to an oath and not fulfil it.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: The group agrees with the Bible that he or she who does not work will come to poverty and that he or she who does not work should not eat.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: The group teaches that Jesus and the Holy Spirit do not support such works of the devil like witchcraft and sorcery. Hence, according to Apostle Paul these evil workers must be openly condemned and rebuked.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: The group accepts the Bible's condemnation of violence of any type either lethal or non-lethal. Jesus even says "Love your enemies, do good to those who hate you, bless those who curse you, and pray for those who abuse you. To one who strikes you on the cheek, offer the other also"

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: The group sees risks as nothing to fear if it arises from divine instruction from the supreme being. They find strength in such biblical passages which says "Be strong and of good courage, do not fear nor be afraid of them; for the Lord your God, He is the One who goes with you. He will not leave you nor forsake you." This verse emphasizes the importance of courage in the face of risk-taking. Abraham even took risk in the Old Testament by taking his only son Isaac for slaughter according to God's instruction.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: The group teaches that all young people should honor their fathers and mothers as the Bible stipulates. They accept the injunction of the bible which requires that leaders should be careful not to rebuke an older man sharply, but appeal to him as you would to a father; treat younger men like brothers. The older women are to be treated like mothers and younger women like sisters, with absolute purity. So, yes, the group requires that members give honor to elders.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: The group upholds the Bible's condemnation of gossip. They draw inspiration from the Bible when it says "A gossip betrays a confidence; so avoid anyone who talks too much." The New Testament calls gossips busybodies. A passage in the New Testament says ... For we hear that there are some which walk among you disorderly, working not at all, but are busybodies. Now them that are such we command and exhort by our Lord Jesus Christ, that with quietness they work, and eat their own bread.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the LORD loves justice and hates robbery with iniquity. They believe the Bible when it says of God that ... I will give them their recompense in truth, and I will make an everlasting covenant with them.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Rituals such as Holy Communion, Water baptism, praying and Fasting and so on are greatly encouraged in the Bible and also practised by Jesus Christ while in the flesh. The group believes in the continuous observance of these practises.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: The church is emphatic about their believe that everything that Jesus did is to be done by the followers who are called Christians all over the world.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus admonished that all Christians should preach the gospel and make disciples of people in Matthew 28:18-20, and Acts 1:8. The group seems true to this instruction left the church by Jesus Christ and keep observing it regularly.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus admonished a fellow during his earthly ministry that "If you would be perfect, go, sell what you possess and give to the poor, and you will have treasure in heaven; and come, follow me." Another portion of the Bible says ... "Share with the Lord's people who are in need. Practice hospitality. The group emphasises these teachings as they encourage members to share their belongings with one another, especially the needy among them.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the supernatural being cares about personal hygiene. , They

quote a portion of the Bible which supports this view. It says, ... therefore, since we have these promises, dear friends, let us purify ourselves from everything that contaminates body and spirit, perfecting holiness out of reverence for God. Some Old Testament books of the Bible discuss extensively about personal hygiene and God's attitude to it

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Caring for the poor, sharing with the Lord's people, practicing hospitality, not being vengeful, praying for those who attempt to harm believers, bearing one another's burdens etc.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that God can punish offenders and can send any supernatural agent to punish an offender

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that Satan and his agents can afflict any person who transgresses the law or injunction of the high god.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that when a person in a household commits an offence, it can affect his or her entire household as in Achan in the Old Testament. They also believe that the sin of a nation can bring disaster upon the citizens.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that Satan and his agents can afflict humans with disasters. They believe the portion of the Bible which says ... The thief comes not, but for to steal, and to kill, and to destroy: I am come that they might have life, and that they might have it more abundantly.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that when people neglect God, they can face dire consequences. They affirm a portion of the Bible (The book of Romans) which says ... And even as they refused to have God in their knowledge, God gave them up unto a reprobate mind, to do those things which are not fitting;

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

Notes: Group norms may not always be what the supernatural beings sanctioned

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: The group affirms that the Bible encourages selflessness. If a person is selfish, he or she might suffer the consequence. They like to draw inspiration from Apostle Paul's letter to the church in Philippi which says ... Do nothing out of selfish ambition or vain conceit. Rather, in humility value others above yourselves, not looking to your own interests but each of you to the interests of the others. They also admonish their members not to withhold good from those who deserve it, when it is in their power to help them.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: The group believes that when there is no sin, there is no punishment.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that all sins will eventually be punished in Hell Fire. They believe that God will punish those who do not acknowledge Him or those who do not obey the gospel of Jesus Christ.

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that all sinners who refuse to repent shall be punished in afterlife.

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - No

Notes: Some punishments can be meted out in this lifetime but final punishment is in afterlife

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - Yes

Notes: The group affirms that every good deed gets rewarded by high god.

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - No

Notes: The group teaches that only the high god rewards any kindness done to others

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes

Notes: The group believes that people can get blessed through the kindness of their forebears. For example, grand and great grandchildren of Abraham are blessed

because of their father Abraham's obedience to high God,

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
– Yes

Notes: The group believes that supernatural rewards are apportioned to those who selfless in their giving. They hold this saying of the Bible to be true ... Give, and it shall be given unto you; good measure, pressed down, and shaken together, and running over, shall men give into your bosom. For with the same measure that you mete withal it shall be measured to you again.

↳ Done randomly:
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus is believed to be the savior and messiah of the whole world

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: An Eschatological belief is present. This religious group believes that some last-day events will occur and will finally usher in the coming of the Messiah (Jesus Christ). The group teaches this biblical concept at every available opportunity to the members to keep abreast with times and seasons as they continue to unfold

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group teaches that intending couples should not engage in sex until marriage is contracted. They also warn their members against stealing, no violence, no cheating and no lying. They teach their members to show compassion, love and kindness to everybody.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: They teach the virtues of loving one another, compassion, lovingkindness, hard work, diligence

and discipline. They also admonish members to embrace patience, humility and meekness. They advocate or preach these virtues to members from time to time.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - Yes
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Yes [specify]: Patience, humility, meekness etc

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Members can marry and enjoy sexual intimacy within the confine of marriage alone. No sex outside marriage .

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Fasting is part of the biblical teaching among the members

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: It is highly forbidden for members of this religious group to engage in permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her

actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: This religious group believes in self preservation and preaches about good health and long life, suicide is condemned as a crime

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: The church has times assigned for the study of the scripture, prayer meeting during the week and church services on Sundays. Night Prayers can even last for six hours.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: This religious group preaches to members to love everybody so as to win them into their fold

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 72

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– Number of participants: 5000

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– Average interval [hours]: 6

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
– Yes
Notes: Wrong interpretation of the scripture is not acceptable and never condoned

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
– Yes
Notes: Members must live according to the teaching of the Scripture

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– No
Notes: Practices are dynamic and people can meet at different places and different times for their generally accepted ritual performance

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– No
Notes: Use of alcohol is not permitted. The religious group leaders preach against use of alcoholic drinks of any form

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: The major tribe that constitute the membership of this religious group is Yoruba of Southwestern Nigeria. There is no doubt that there are few other minor tribes like Ibo and Benin speaking people of Nigeria

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: The group gives relief from time to time.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The group has an inbuilt welfare structure for the poor and not well-to-do members

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, a welfare purse is made available at the central and local levels of the organization

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Not yet but it is in the pipeline. The group has plans to begin such gestures to the elderly and infirm in the future.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group has elementary school, High School and Bible College where members can learn about formal education

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group is hierarchized such as church pastors and leaders, Area Pastors and leaders, Zonal Pastors and Leaders, before Assistant General Overseers and Deputy General Overseers and ;lastly the General Overseer. It is however not a rigid arrangement. A member may choose to interact directly with the overall head and bypass other leaders below the overall leader

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: Not yet but there is a future plan

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: During the religious group collective program, each church is expected to provide transport for the members that could not afford to attend the program due to financial constrain

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: It is expected that each member pay tithes of 10% of their income every month or if business people every time profits are made

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: State and Federal Government levied taxes on members who have businesses and people who work for governments

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Yes

Notes: They are armless corps known as Christ Way Ministries Corps

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: When a big program that will involve a large number of people is involved

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: If there is any need for judicial matters

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Criminal or legal offences are usually referred to the government officials responsible for that.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: If the offence is a grievous one but the religious group has not had such a case since it has been founded

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Notes: Nigerian legal system has discouraged corporal punishment

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: If the situation warrants it, for example, if a person owes, his or her properties may be seized until full payment of the debt is made.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Religious group is part of larger society so every member is subject to formal institutional legal code instituted by the government.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members can enrol in institutionalized military if they want

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: every member is subject to institutionalized military provided by the government

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members can speak English, Yoruba and any other languages they have learnt to speak.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As at present English and Yoruba are the written languages used by the members

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The group prepares a year planner annually. It serves to notify of the group programs for the year and to assist everyone prepare for such programs.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There is a public calendar that also guides the religious group's members' activities

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members can engage in small scale farming or large scale depending on their capacities. However, members buy their foods from the public space just like other people in the larger society

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Patoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)